

**THE SKILL OF ISAAC ASIMOV AND HOJIAKBAR SHAYXOV IN
DESCRIBING THE PSCHY OF THE HERO**

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**AYZEK AZIMOV VA HOJIAKBAR SHAYXOVNING QAHRAMON
RUHIYATINI YARATISH MAHORATI**

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**МАСТЕРСТВО АЙЗАКА АСИМОВА И ХОДЖИАКБАРА ШАЙХОВА
В ОПИСАНИИ ПСИХИИ ГЕРОЯ**

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Abstract: In this article, the psyche of the hero in the novels of the American fiction writer Isaac Asimov and the Uzbek fiction writer Khojiakbar Shaykhov is comparatively studied, and their ability to reveal the hero's psyche is scientifically and theoretically confirmed.

Key words: hero's mentality, fantastic literature, Isaac Asimov, Khojiakbar Shaykhov, criticism, plot, novel, interpretation.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Amerika fantast yozuvchisi Ayzek Azimov va O'zbek fantastik yozuvchisi Hojiakbar Shayxov romanlarida qahramon ruhiyati qiyosiy aspektda o'rganilib, ularning qahramon ruhiyatini ochish mahorati ilmiy-nazariy jihatdan tadqiq etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: qahramon ruhiyati, fantastik adabiyot, Ayzek Azimov, Hojiakbar Shayxov, tanqid, syujet, roman, talqin.

Аннотация: В данной статье сравнительно исследуется психика героя в романах американского фантаста Исаака Азимова и узбекского фантаста Ходжиакбара Шайхова, научно и теоретически подтверждается их способность раскрывать психику героя.

Ключевые слова: психология героя, фантастическая литература, Айзек Азимов, Ходжиакбар Шайхов, критика, сюжет, роман, интерпретация.

Introduction:

In the works of fiction, the author's worldview, attitude to social life, goals and tasks, philosophical approach are expressed with the help of the image of literary heroes. In general, a hero is a person who is famous for his courage, bravery, and bravery, applied to the main participants. Because any negative character is woven into a literary work, it is certain that he plays a key role in the occurrence of an event in the work.

Zamiyatin has the following thoughts about the psyche of the hero: "It is known that in every work the author describes the feelings and adventures of his characters.

In this case, the skill of the writer is determined by the extent to which he was able to show the inner world of the characters of his work. It will be possible to see the images of the feelings of these artistic heroes, their experiences directly in monologic speeches or dialogues. In addition, the actions and gestures of the hero, as well as the tone of speech, are also reflected in artistic elements" [1].

In literary works written in all genres, the writer introduces to the reader all the emotions experienced by his characters, whether it is happiness or suffering, internal experiences, by skillfully describing the inner psyche of the hero of the work. Some researchers do not consider psychology as a way to discover the inner world of a person. Therefore, in the study of the mental world of the hero, psychologism is considered not a method, but a unique image of the psyche in fiction" [2]. When describing the inner world of a writer's hero, it is evaluated based on how deeply he was able to understand his heart. The writer uses two types of forms to describe the mental state and character of his hero: internal and external forms. In the internal form, the writer uses monologues, memories, associations, and images of the imagination to illuminate the hero, and in the external form, he describes using facial expressions and other states of appearance that show the emotional uniqueness of the psyche. Together with this, the same mental state of the hero of the author's work can be described in different ways, i.e. directly and indirectly. When describing the psyche of the hero directly, the writer enters the inner world of the hero, that is, his heart. In most cases, the author uses the character's oral or otherwise written inner speech or dream. In the case of indirect description, the author can use external factors, such as gestures and behavior, to describe the inner world of the hero.

Material and Research Methods

The reason why the works of Isaac Asimov and Khojiakbar Shaykhov were chosen as objects for analysis is that Isaac Asimov has a great contribution to the rapid development of the genre of fiction in American literature, and Khojiakbar Shaykhov is recognized as one of the first creators of the fiction genre of Uzbek literature.

Isaac Asimov is one of the greatest fantasy writers of the 20th century. His story "The Liar" is about a mind-reading robot, long before the advent of modern lie detectors and the fields of artificial intelligence. The work that made Isaac Asimov famous beyond the borders of his country and all over the world was about robots. This work called "I-Robot" is completely different from previous works about robots written by other writers. At the same time, unlike other authors who tell stories about mechanical creatures that fight against humankind, Isaac Asimov depicts robots as close assistants of humankind, helpers that lighten the burden, and provides many practical ideas for those who are involved in robotics. Robots in Asimov's works can be said to be more humane and humane than their masters in some places.

Despite the fact that Khojiakbar Shaykhov is an engineer by profession, he started his career as a photographer. He became widely known not only in Uzbekistan, but also in the world literary arena with his fantastic stories, short stories, and novels. His works won awards and translated into many languages. O. Sharafiddinov writes: "Khojiakbar Shaykhov can be called one of the swallows of Uzbek science fiction literature... Why should a writer who created in the second half of the 20th century be called one of the swallows who started Uzbek science fiction? ! The reason for this is that earlier fiction was seen as an element of creativity, but in a certain period it was a full-fledged, independent piece of creativity, with its own subject area, its own image tools, its own poetics, it begins to form as a genre... Because, by this century, the role of science in the life of society has expanded immeasurably.... Thus, when it came to the middle of the 20th century, fantastic literature began to flourish all over the world.... The spring of the science fiction genre had begun in Uzbek literature. One of the swallows who led this spring was Khojiakbar Shaykhov" [3].

The heroes of Khojiakbar Shaykhov's works "Connected Worlds" and "Two Worlds of Troubles" can see the worlds that we cannot see with our eyes with the eyes of our hearts. The main theme of the novel "Connected Worlds" is to awaken a person from the sleep of heedlessness and achieve perfection. The main characters of the novel

are sisters named Nazira, Nargiza, Nafisa. The writer describes these sisters as people with fantastic characteristics. That is, they have the ability to foresee the future and communicate with the souls of the great saints of the past. The spirits of dear saints such as Hazrat Ghavsul Azam, Sheikh Tahir, Haja Asrar Wali, Tilla Sheikh also participate in the work and they support the three sisters. Shaykhov's second novel in this series - "Two World of Troubles" continues the events of the first novel and is devoted to the current problems of our time, universal, spiritual and spiritual issues. In this novel, the bodies of the main characters Nazira and Nafisa are used by saints. The novel also contains the images of criminals who, along with brother Saidmansur, a valiant fighter for the Motherland, for its freedom, ex-fighter Rakhmatillo and scientist Asadbek, created a fake political party and wanted to carry out malicious intentions and evil deeds. It is depicted that a person commits many sins and sinks into the mire of pleasure and remains unaware that he is hitting his own foot with an axe.

Results and Discussions:

The speech of the author plays an important role in the analysis of the mental state of the characters in the works of fiction. "The author's speech often expresses plot exposition, landscape imagery, and psychological states of characters" [4]. A fantastic work, just like a work of art, cannot fail to show its influence on the world of imagination, thinking, the expansion of the scope of thinking, and the growth of speech. Therefore, it is not without reason that Ray Bradbury notes that "everything in the history of mankind begins with a dream"[5].

Isaac Asimov and Khojiakbar Shaykhov often try to show the mental state of their characters through their speech. Therefore, it can be felt that the speech of the hero of the work is aimed at revealing the psyche of both the owner of the speech and the character to whom the speech is directed. In works of art, speech is very important in revealing the psyche of each character. This importance is also reflected in the works of fiction. Regardless of whether the hero of a fictional work is real or fantastic, the aspects of artistic psychology, in particular, speech, allow illuminating the inner world

of the characters of a fictional work and the world of his imagination, like a reflection in a mirror. As the imagination is the priority in the works of fantasy, it has common aspects and peculiarities with the works of other genres. Moreover, the responsibility of persuasion is twofold.

Isaac Asimov's novel "The Currents of Space" begins with the protagonist's dissatisfaction with his current situation. As soon as the work begins, the psyche of the hero is described. We can see that the hero's displeasure is expressed by the writer's cold and dark sky and the hero's own speech in the following passage: "The man from Earth came to a decision. It had been slow in coming and developing, but it was here. It had been weeks since he had felt the comforting deck of his ship and the cool, dark blanket of space about it. Originally, he had intended a quick report to the local office of the Interstellar Spatio-analytic Bureau and a quicker retreat to space. Instead, he had been held here. It was almost like a prison."

Khojiakbar Shaykhov's work "Connected worlds" begins with a landscape image. "Navruz came to ancient Tashkent's genius of Hazrati Azam by melting cold winter ice. As if unable to absorb the fact that the ancient tradition rooted in our soil has been persecuted for a long time, the cold, flesh-shaking winds do not stop at night. During the day, the city is shrouded in white and thick fog, and around noon, like a bride the sun open come out of." [6].

The author begins the work with a description of a natural landscape, and the purpose of this is because the work is based on the mutual struggle of real and fantastic individuals and groups. The disparity between materiality and spirituality in the work is the use of landscape to reflect their influence on each other. The image of evil in the play be it fictional or real, prepares for the inevitability of the celebration of positive images over negative images, like an overture in music played before the start of a performance.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, we can see Uzbek features in Khojiakbar Shaykhov's novels and the images he created. One of the main differences between him and Asimov's creative style is that in Shaykhov's works we find aspects specific to our religion and nation. Novels such as "Connected Worlds" and "Two Worlds of Troubles" can be a clear example of this. The issues of time and space are different in the works of both artists. In Asimov's stories, events mostly take place in the future in space. Shaykhov's stories describe the discoveries that humanity will face in the future. By referring to Shaykhov's field of astronomy, he wants to show the level of development of this field in our country in the future. In this place, Asimov expressed his scientific predictions through his works, and they are really coming true. Robot technology is a clear example of this.

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